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Experiencing the Depth and Diversity of Reality: Ongoing Questions and Not a Full Stop

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Abstract: The article focusses on some of the important questions and examine them deeply. Socratics has rightly said, '*an unexamined life is not worth living*'. An examined life helps us to lead a better life, opens up our eyes to differentiate what is good and bad; it also leads us to know ourselves better. Moreover, it helps us recognize *the beauty of the world, mystery of the body and holiness of the other*. This will make us approachable, loving, kind, and humble human beings. It explores the Holy Science model, according to which everything God created, including science, religion and evil itself, is good and holy. They have their own independence existence and domain. But they all lead to the final TRUTH. For this constant searching and questioning from all dimensions of our existence are essential.

Keywords: Depth of Reality, Holy Science Model, Truth, Questioning

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Philosophy or the deep thinking begins with asking questions. This was the important method of the great Philosopher, Socrates. He often entertained the questions but rarely gave any answers for the questions, he was asked. Karl Popper also believed that the problems or the questions are more important than the answers (Funelas, 2001). For most of the time the answers depend on the questions. Asking question is one of the very important means to learn and unlearn. The moment we begin to question, we start learning. On the other hand, when we stop asking questions, we put end to our learning. Therefore we need to constantly ask questions to know the depth of reality. To know the depth of the reality we need to have ongoing questions and not a full stop.

The aim of this paper is to focus on some of the important questions and examine them deeply. Socrates has rightly said, '*an unexamined life is not worth living*'. An examined life helps us to lead a better life, opens up our eyes to differentiate what is good and bad; it also leads us to know ourselves better. Moreover it helps us recognize *the beauty of the world, mystery of the body and holiness of the other*. This will make us approachable, loving, kind, and humble human beings.

The more we ask questions, the more we learn.

The more we learn, the wiser we become.

The wiser we are, the more humble we become.

The more humble we are, the more human we become.

The more human we are, the more divine we become.

Ultimately this is what we are all called for, the purpose of our life.

Approaching the Truth of Reality

Different thinkers have different views on the truth of reality. According to Hegel the absolute is not yet but the reality is in

the process of becoming itself. (Mercier, 2020: 103). According to Gandhi the reality or Truth is God and God alone is the reality (or Truth)! According to Plato the ideal world is the only reality and everything else is copy.

From the given examples it is clear that the reality is different to the different thinkers. And this reality is completely subjective. There are two kinds of reality; *subjective* and *objective*. The subjective reality is based on the personal experiences whereas the objective reality is based on universality; reality in itself. Our task in this paper is to find out the objective reality which exists independent of the knower.

What is truth? Who can know it? Where can it be found? How does the truth look like? These are some of the fundamental questions of the metaphysics.

None has ever objectively claimed what the reality or truth is all about. But one thing is for sure, the reality exists; and that is the only truth. The truth can never be false and unreal. The truth is single and one. The way or the method to reach the truth may differ but ultimately the truth is one. But the questions here are: *What is truth? Who can know it? Where can it be found? How does the truth look like?* These are some of the fundamental questions of the metaphysics and of our very life. To respond to the stated questions, let's examine some of the important issues.

The Mystery of Human Body

We are all human beings. We are human because we have the power of rationality to understand and act on our will. Though we have the element of understanding and rationality in us we are unable to understand many things happening daily in and around us. We don't understand how and when our hairs and nails grow. We don't know why do we blink every time. We are unaware of what happens to our body in sleep. We cannot explain why do we

dream at night and where do they come from. We see the exact places and the persons in our dreams as we have already seen through our eyes. It is beyond our reach what is that which articulate the exact images and places even in our dreams. We don't even feel the circulations of our body unless we check them. We really don't know where do our life or soul lay; whether is it in our blood, in our heart, in our brain or any other parts of our body. Without our awareness, without even any struggle (when we are normal) how do we breathe each moment. We don't know how the thoughts come to our minds. Therefore, human body is called the palace of mystery.

The Mystery of Universe and Human Being

There are two extremes of thoughts for the beginning of the universe and of the human beings. According to *science*, taking the theory of Big-Bang, the universe came into being by *prime atom*. And according to Charles Darwin, the human being originated from very lower life form, the apes (James, 1985: 257). On the process of their living on earth the apes adopted the shape of the present day human beings. And whatever survived remained till today. He called it, therefore, the survival of the fittest. The *religious*, taking the Christian view, on the other hand is just the opposite of this extreme of thought. It claims that universe is created by God or the Supreme Being.

As we know the truth is only one, therefore, whatever the explanation and logic we apply for the creation of the whole universe and of the human being, the truth remains the same, i.e. the universe and the human beings exist. The above given two extremes of thoughts show that we are unaware of the how the universe and the human beings came into existence. To find out this same reality there came up so many myths and theories and are they exist even to this day. But still the

beginning of the universe and emergence of human beings on the surface of the earth is a mystery.

The Mystery of the World

Till date what we know about this universe, is what is discovered. The science has discovered only 4% of the universe and 96% of the universe is yet to be discovered. The celestial world has been discovered in very small measure. We have come to know only about some of the galaxies and stars of the celestial world. We don't know if there are another earths, suns, moons, and planets in the other galaxies. We have discovered only seven colours till today but it does not mean there are only seven colours. Among these seven colours only one or two are can be seen by some of the birds and the animals. There are some rays which we can perceive, it does not mean there are only that many rays or waves. We are aware of only the five senses in our body; it does not mean there are only five senses in our body (Pandikattu, 2015: 214-217). It is because we have not yet discovered.

And those which are discovered are also not very reliable. Someone in future may come out with the new discovery for the very same things and falsify what we believe to be true. For, we know that whatever have been discover is justified and falsified every now and then. For the first time, through the theory of Issac Newton we knew that the things fall to the ground because of the gravitational force but later Albert Einstein came up saying that it is so because of the curvature of time and space caused by mass and energy. In the same way the understanding of the world changed from geocentric to heliocentric, understanding of minute particle from atom to quark, and the understanding of light from particle to wave-particle. But the *Science* has clearly claimed that it is always open for the change. Till date science says that the life is possible only on earth but what will happen tomorrow is a mystery.

Knowing the Truth of Reality

According to the well-known Indian philosopher Sankara this world is the ‘*Maya*’. He says that the world is false and unreal, therefore the multiple and changing reality perceived by our senses are not real world (Mercier, 2000: 107). The finite is the non-absolute being and the infinite is the absolute Being (Mercier, 2000: 108). Therefore, the infinite Being and things cannot be perceived by the finite being. We, finite beings, know only the limited things since our knowledge of what exist in the physical world rests on empirical evidence (Maudlin, 2007: 78). For Aquinas all human knowledge is drawn from the sensible world, which is known by the intellect in a way that it cannot be known by any sensory world (James, 1985: 104). This is the reason why we don’t even come to know many things what is happening in our surroundings unless someone comes up to us and tells us or unless we come to know through different means of communication. And what we come to know by ourselves also many a times is beyond our understanding. From the above discussions also we have come to know that humans are far from the knowledge of even the simplest things happening in and around us. Therefore to know the truth as it is, it is beyond our comprehension. We are unaware, not because our life span here on earth is short but we finite beings can never know the reality even if we had to live for the thousands of years.

According to the French scientist-theologian, Teilhard de Chardin (Feist 2017) , to know everything as it is, is to know the mind of God, in other words to know the mind of God is to know everything. The God/ Ultimate Being who is all powerful and omnipresence alone can give the perfect and the absolute answer for everything of this vast universe. As for us, it is impossible to know even the most common things of this world. As the poem goes this way:

Your creation is so amazing O Lord,
If I think, I don't understand them
If I see, I don't perceive them
If I look at your creation
My eyes are not satisfied.
How and why do the flowers have many colours?
How and why have some fruits sweetness in them?
How and why do the snakes have poison in their mouth?
How and why do the silkworms have silk in them?
How and why do the glow-worms have light in them?
How and why is the sky on high?
How and why are the clouds in the sky?
How and why is the rain hidden in the clouds?
How and why do the oysters have pearls in them?
How and why is the gold buried beneath the earth?
How and why do the fruits have seeds?
How and why do the seeds have trees inside them?
How and why do the flowers have the good smells in them?
How and why do the leaves have greenness in them?
I really don't understand them.

Holy Science model is one of the means to come closer to the one who created vast universe which is beyond our understanding and reach.

Holy Science Model

The Holy Science Model holds that everything created by God is good and holy. It holds that from a believer's point of view, everything, including science and religion are created by God. Therefore, they are essentially good and holy. The different discoveries of the things, religious experiences and the amazing creation of this world lead us to the creator. The world and the universe are so beautiful and amazing to behold, and it is out of our understanding. Each object or created things of this world leads us towards its creator. The essence of that creator is present

in each and every created thing. Without the creator, there will not be any creatures, at least from a religious point of view.

The Holy Science Model holds:

1. No truth can contradict the other truth
2. Any addition to knowledge is progress
3. God is the culmination of this process
4. Therefore, the more we know the world, the closer we get to know God.

According to Aristotle, Thomas Aquinas and Teilhard, the wonders of this material world lead us to the spiritual world. Every particular object of the world is introducing the highest being who has created them. Thomas Aquinas came up with five proofs for God's existence and four causes through the material means. It is sure that there exists an agent whom we call God, Supreme Being, Ultimate Being or Absolute Being who created everything. For you everything is crystal and clear. Before Him and nothing is hidden from his sight. The agent knows everything about the created. As this poem goes;

For me everything is dim and unclear
But YOU know everything is crystal-clear.
YOU know the number of.....
Stars in heaven,
Sands in the sea shore,
Hairs in our heads,
Our living on earth,
Leaves in thick trees.

YOU know how many times.....
Our heart beats a day,
We think in a day,
We take the steps in life.
YOU know.....

What makes us happy,
What makes us sad,
What makes and what breaks us.

From this perspective, we do hold that God is the highest and noblest of all. But we can find traces of his goodness and holiness in everything: in the creatures, in religions and in sciences. The same goodness and holiness can be found in everyone, including the atheists. The evil person also somehow carries this same divinity, though we do not understand how evil can be called holy.

This model does give significance and ultimacy to God. But it does not say that religion is superior to science. It does not hold that the other-worldly is more important than this worldly. Both have their own autonomous and independent existence. They have their own laws, methods and goals. But ultimately, they all lead to the one TRUTH. Towards this TRUTH we keep on moving, with the help of good and evil, sorrowful and happy, theists and atheists. For we all search together, as members of the human family towards that TRUTH, which remains dim and blurred. Even in this haziness and dimness, we can trace the HOLY.

Conclusion

Through the above discussion, we conclude that everything before our eyes are mystery. And we all know that mystery can never be solved but only explored. The reality of the *world, thing and the universe* are beyond our perception and our comprehension. We can never arrive at our reality or truth (destination) fully; ours is a pilgrimage towards an ever-receding horizon (Pandikattu, 2018:5). To know the truth as it is, is never possible for the finite being now and in the future too. Therefore, we can only approach the reality but we can never attain it; in other word we can only come closer to the reality or truth but never know them. We cannot give any answer for anything, for

answer is “once-and-for-all” but we can only respond; for the responses can be many for the same thing. Since we are unable to find the answer, it does not mean that we should stop asking questions. When we ask questions, we shall definitely come to know, at least, some jest of reality.

Humans are called to be the explorers of the world by asking penetrating questions on the nature of reality. Our life here on earth is an ongoing journey to come closer to the reality. Towards the end of his life, even St. Thomas Aquinas kept silent because he discovered whatever he wrote was rubbish and useless. The reality is much greater and more marvellous than what he wrote and knew. Through this it is evident that reality remains a mystery. Therefore, let the questions be important for us never put full stop to it. This will definitely help us to appreciate the mystery and goodness of the universe and human being. And we keep on asking, exploring and waiting. In this sense, life has no full stops. It is a series of questions that goes beyond everything, including our own death! In this sense, we can know the depth, diversity, colour and complexity of the reality, which is very much part of our own selves

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